

Consumer Awareness Towards Online Shopping with Special Reference to Sivagangai District

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Abstract: In this era of fast moving lifestyle, customers are busier than what they were few years back. It is precisely for this reason customers are also purchasing their products and services through online shopping. It is this sense that e-entrepreneurs have successfully targeted upon through 'deal sites' like Amazon, snapdeal, flipkart, shopclues, etc. On-line shopping will become the future of shopping world. There are so many companies who are doing online business of different product & services. It gives the better option to online customers to easily identify the products and their prices on the website in the global market. Both primary and secondary has been used for the study. The primary data were collected from 150 respondents in sivagangai district by using simple random sampling method. The tools used for the analysis such as Factor analysis, Friedman test and Anova. The results shows that middle age group people were using more online shopping and most of the customers have highly aware about amazon websites.

Keywords: fast moving lifestyle, online shopping, online customers Amazon, snapdeal, flipkart, shopclues.

1. INTRODUCTION

Business activity is a shopping activity in which a customer peruses the available of goods or services presented by one or more retailers with the intent to purchase a suitable selection from the retailers or sellers. It is the process of bought goods or services and exchange money or money transfer method. Now days there are two channels available for business methods. One is online or e-business and another one offline or traditional business. Online business is one of the most popular ways to make buying and selling of goods and services. It is act of purchasing products or services through over the Internet. But offline business is a traditional way of buying goods and services. It depends upon customers who select which channel they follow for shopping. It's an era of technology so public that is customers, they want to take the advantage of that thing and prefer online shopping, but still there are some people who don't trust online business activities and they would like prefer offline business activities.

In this research paper the researcher focuses towards online shopping. On-line shopping is a recent phenomenon in the field of E-Business and is definitely going to be the future of shopping in the world. Most of the companies are running their on-line portals to sell their products/services on-line. The facility of Online purchasing has allowed customers to identify the different types of products available in the global market, Due to rapid globalization, all types of products are available on the internet .Goods and services, consumer durables, books, audio and video cassettes and services like and air tickets can also be purchased online. The paper aims to study about the consumer awareness towards online shopping.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Dr.C.Subramanian & M.Jayalakshmi(2020)¹, in their article said that consumer perception and awareness towards online shopping in Nagapattinam district, the main objective of the study is to analyze the awareness of consumers in online shopping . The researcher suggested that online store may offer customer on e-wallet which transfer balance from customer online bank account to the store payment system and the researcher also suggested that the online marketers should deliver right color, quality and quantity product order by the consumers. It will improve the customer satisfaction in order to increase online trading.

Muthupriya(2019)² in their article said that “A study on customers satisfaction towards online shopping in sivagangai district” the main objective of the study is to find out the satisfaction level of the customer for online purchase. The respondents are selected based on convenient sampling. The researcher concluded that online shopping is becoming more popular day by day with the increase in the usage of World Wide Web known as www. Understanding customer’s need for online selling has become challenge for marketers. Specially understanding the consumer’s attitudes towards online shopping, making improvement in the factors that influence consumers to shop online and working on factors that affect consumers to shop online will help marketers to gain the competitive edge over others. In conclusion, having access to online shopping has truly revolutionized and influenced our society as a whole.

Parveen Kumar Garg (2018)³, in their article examined that “customers awareness towards online shopping”, the main objectives of the study is to analyze the awareness level of the customers towards online shopping. Primary data has been collected from various respondents like business persons, service persons and students. The researcher has selected convenience sampling method. The total sample size for the study is 500. The researcher concluded that, majority of the consumers were high awareness towards online shopping in Punjab.

Syed et.al (2008)⁴, in their article said that “ Young customers online shopping : An Empirical study”, analyzed that there were four key factors which affected the young consumers’ perceptions towards online shopping that those factors were website design, website reliability, customers’ service and privacy. The very important factor that was affect customers’ behaviour towards online shopping was trust, reliability which is everything for the buyers.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The Main objective of the study is to analyze the customer awareness towards online shopping with special reference to sivagangai district.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The study is based on both primary and secondary data. The data required for the study have been collected through 150 respondents. For the purpose of collection of primary data, a well-structured questionnaire was framed which was filled by the respondents. Required data have been also collected from various books, magazines, journals and websites. The Simple random sample method is selected for the study. The respondents are included students, professionals, officials, business people and others out of questionnaires distributed and collected in sivagangai district.

5. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY:

The study is conducted to bring out the consumer awareness on online-shopping in sivagangai district. The study can explain how the customer selects online-shopping. This study reveals the customers ideas about the online -shopping services. The study gives suggestion that help the manufactures or dealers to increase their online -shopping marketing services.

6. DATA ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION:

The demographic profiles such as gender, age, occupation and Income were given in below table 1.1

Table 1.1: Demographic Profile of the Respondents

GENDER	RESPONSE	PERCENTAGE
GENDER		
Male	67	45
Female	83	55
Total	150	100
AGE		
Below 20 years	70	47
21 to 30 years	32	21
31 to 40 years	30	20
41 to 50 years	18	12
TOTAL	150	100
OCCUPATION		
Salaried	90	60
Business man	30	20
Farmer	20	13

Others	10	7
Total	150	100
INCOME		
Below Rs.10000	10	7
Rs. 10000 to 15000	40	26
Rs. 20000 to 25000	10	7
Above Rs. 25000	90	60
Total	150	100

Source: Primary data

[1] Out of 150 respondents 67% of customers are male members'. Remaining 83% of customers are female members. Hence it could be said that female members are purchasing through online shopping

[2] Out of 150 respondents 47% of sample respondents are belong to the age group below 20 years. 21% are belongs to age group between 21 to 30 years. 20% are belongs to 31 to 40 years and remaining 12% are belongs to 41 to 50 years. Therefore, majority of them were middle age group people.

[3] Out of 150 respondents 60% were salaried customers .20% are doing business and 13% belong to the category of farmers .7% are engaged in other occupation. But more number of salaried people are using online shopping.

[4] Out of 150 customers contacted, majority of customers i.e 60% belonged to Above Rs.25000 income category, 26% of customers earned Rs.10,000 to Rs.15,000 and remaining 10% of customers earned below Rs.10,000 Majority of middle income customers earned above Rs.25000.

6.1 AWARENESS LEVEL OF THE RESPONDENTS ON VARIOUS WEBSITE AVAILABLE FOR BUYING THE GOODS- FRIEDMAN TEST:

In recent days, online shopping Initiative impulse the people doing all the business transaction in online and having the direct impact on buying behaviour the goods. Online e-tailers are utilizing the opportunity of changing customer behaviour and sentiments and offering all the goods through the online platform. In order to assess the awareness level of the respondents towards various online e-tailers, friedman test have been applied. Friedman test is one of the non parametric tests. Friedman test is used for identifying whether there is any significant difference in the ranks provided by respondents about the awareness level on various online platforms available for buying the goods in online.

The null hypothesis is that there exists no significant difference in the mean ranks provided by the respondents about the awareness level on various online platforms available for buying the goods in online.

Table 1.2: Awareness level of the respondents on various website available for buying the goods- Friedman test

Websites	Mean Rank	Chi-Square	Df	Significant Level at 0.05 (N=663)
Amazon	10.32	1865.811	12	.001
Flipkart.com	8.38			
Jabong	7.14			
Yebme	6.17			
Ebay	5.89			
Infibeam	5.12			
Snapdeal	7.27			
Cilory	6.06			
Koovs	5.01			
Myntra	6.34			
Shopclues	5.31			
HomeShop	4.85			

Source: Using Spss statistics

Since P value of .001 is less than the standardised bench mark value of .05, so the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence it is concluded that there is a significance difference between mean ranks provided by the respondents about the awareness level on various websites available for buying fashion products. Based on the mean rank amazon (10.32) is the top level awareness websites by the customers in the study area, followed by flipkart (8.38), snapdeal (7.27), Jabong (7.14), Myntra (6.34), Yebme (6.17), Cilory (6.06), Ebay (5.89), Shopclues (5.31), Infibeam (5.12), Koovs (5.01) and the last rank is assigned to HomeShop (4.85).

6.2 CONSUMER AWARENESS TOWARDS ONLINE SHOPPING - FACTOR ANALYSIS:

Factor analysis is a multivariable statistical technique that explains the inter relationship among the total set of observed variables. Factor analysis is a way of grouping of variables based on the inertia of common characteristics which would serve as a common denominator for such as a classification. It is an analytical tool, which can aid in the preliminary investigation and in the interpretation of the relationship among a large number of inter- related and inter – dependent variables. The primary purpose of factor analysis is the resolution of a set of observed variables in terms of new categories called factors. Factor analysis may be useful for any one of the following functions.

[1] It can point out the latent factors or dimensions that determine the relationship among a set of observed or manifest values.

[2] Secondly the factor analysis is useful when things need to be grouped.

[3] Finally, Factor analysis can be used for empirical clustering of observations.

The respondents were asked to provide their opinion in the scaling of strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, and strongly disagree. The researcher has used the multivariate technique by name factor analysis in order to classify the related variables. This test can be applied only after finding out the suitability of data. Hence, **Kaiser – Mayer – Olkin (KMO)** is used to check the adequacy and suitability of the data for factor analysis. The test measures sampling adequacy for each variable in the analysis. The sample size is always more the data is appropriate for the factor analysis.

There are 20 factors which involved the awareness level towards online shopping. In order to group the related variables, the researcher has decided to use the factor analysis. Before grouping the variable, the normality has to be ascertained. Hence for ascertaining the normality, KMO has been used. The (KMO) measures of sampling adequacy index are used to examine whether the data are appropriate to examine the factor analysis. The value below 0.5 imply that the factor analysis is not appropriate, either to collect more data or to rethink which variables to include. If the KMO value lies between .7 and .8, it is good for factoring. Bartlett’s test of sphericity is a test statistics used to examine the shape of normal distribution and also verify the smoothness of the curve. Table 1.3 explains the test they are Kaiser – Mayer – Olkin (KMO) measures of sampling adequacy and Bartlett’s test of sphericity. It gives the statistics of KMO, Bartlett’s test of sphericity and chi-square analysis of association, degrees of freedom and the probability value.

Table 1.3: Kaiser – Mayer – Olkin (KMO) Bartlett’s Test

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.831
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	534.279
	Df	54
	Sig.	.000

Source: Primary Data

Table 1.3 Shows that the KMO Value of 0.831, which indicates that the degree of common variance among the variables is quite high, therefore factor analysis can be conducted.

6.3 CONSUMER AWARENESS TOWARDS ONLINE SHOPPING - FACTOR ANALYSIS – COMMUNALITIES:

The principle component analysis has been administered for grouping the factors of consumers’ awareness level towards online shopping. It is a method of data reduction. The proportion of the variance of a particular item due to common factor is called as communality. The initial value of the communality in a principle component analysis is 1. The extraction communalities estimate the variance in each variable accounted for the factors in the factor solution. The value is less than .5 which indicates the variables that do not fit well with the factor solution and should possibly be dropped from the analysis.

Table 1.4 shows that extraction value of the respondents’ towards consumers’ awareness level towards online shopping.

Table 1.4: Consumers’ awareness level towards online shopping – Communalities

Components	Initial	Extraction
I know groceries items are available in online shopping	1.000	.826
Furniture items are available in online shopping.	1.000	.551
I am aware of that the payments can be made on delivery of the products.	1.000	.683
Clothing and shoes can be bought through internet.	1.000	.773
Home decor items like flower and vases, clocks, lights, lamps, handicrafts, paintings, wall art, etc..are available in online shopping.	1.000	.525
Kitchen items like dinner sets, coffee mugs, cutlery, bar accessories, cooker, kitchen storage.etc. can be purchased through internet.	1.000	.679
Home furnishings like bed sheets, carpets, bedcovers, rugs, towels, etc.. are available in online shopping.	1.000	.830
Electronic items can be purchased in online shopping.	1.000	.568
Kids toys are also available in online shopping.	1.000	.775
Jewelleries are available in online websites.	1.000	.684
Accessories like watches, sunglasses, belts, eyeglasses, wallets, pens, keychains, etc. also can be purchased over internet.	1.000	.746
Availability of holiday bookings (Resorts/Rooms)	1.000	.697
Availability of travel tickets.	1.000	.696
Availability of entertainment tickets.	1.000	.536
Books and Magazines can also be purchased in internet shopping.	1.000	.544
Internet banking can be used for online shopping.	1.000	.742
Defective or wrong products can be returned back or exchanged in online shopping.	1.000	.738
Online orders can be tracked until it is delivered.	1.000	.645
No installation charges for installable items.	1.000	.781
Online retailers should have secure payment certificate to assure that the payments are safe.	1.000	.689

Source: Primary Data

Table 1.4 explicit the variance of the twenty variables ranging from .600 to 0.891. It shows that the nine variables exhibit the considerable variance from 50 percent to 90 percent. Hence it could be concluded that all these variables are capable of segmenting themselves with respect to the consumer awareness level towards online shopping.

6.4 CONSUMER AWARENESS TOWARDS ONLINE SHOPPING - TOTAL VARIANCE:

The total variance analysis is important to know the rotated sum of square value. The rotated three factors are determined based on the total Eigen value if the factor should be greater than one. The total cumulative variance is explained by the total percentage of variance by each retained four factors. **Table 1.5** gives the individual variance of the predominant factors which emerged out of twenty factors.

Table 1.5: Consumer Awareness level towards online shopping – Total Variance

Total Variance Explained						
Component	Initial Eigen values			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	5.883	39.223	39.223	4.157	27.712	27.712
2	1.586	10.574	49.797	2.366	15.771	43.483
3	1.132	7.546	57.343	1.861	12.407	55.890
4	1.010	6.737	64.079	1.228	8.189	64.079
5	.990	6.599	70.678			

6	.926	6.176	76.854			
7	.796	5.308	82.162			
8	.608	4.057	86.219			
9	.560	3.733	87.948			
10	.448	2.988	88.941			
11	.551	1.581	89.356			
12	.356	2.682	90.821			
13	.842	2.542	92.631			
14	.721	3.652	93.562			
15	.564	.889	94.362			
16	.341	2.275	95.215			
17	.285	1.898	97.113			
18	.214	1.424	98.537			
19	.116	.771	99.309			
20	.104	.691	100.000			
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.						

As could be seen from the Table 1.5, Eigen values are greater than one for different factors. From this one, it is confirmed that, the twenty factors are grouped into different predominant factors. The rotated sum of squared loading should be greater than 50 percent. The twenty variables are reduced in to four predominant factors with the individual variances of **27.712, 43.483, 55.890 and 64.079**. It is also found that the total variance of 9 variables is greater than one. Moreover it confirms that the factor segment is the meaningful one. Hence it is confirmed that factor analysis is meaningful one.

6.5 CONSUMER AWARENESS TOWARDS ONLINE SHOPPING - ROTATED COMPONENT MATRIX:

Rotated component matrix is useful to identify the groups among the twenty variables of consumer awareness towards online shopping. Table 1.6 explains the rotated component matrix result of the factor analysis.

Table 1.6: Consumer Awareness towards online shopping - Rotated component matrix

Factors	1	2	3	4
I know groceries items are available in online shopping	.842			
Furniture items are available in online shopping.	.781			
Books and Magazines can also be purchased in internet shopping.	.632			
Clothing and shoes can be bought through internet.	.986			
Home decor items like flower and vases, clocks, lights, lamps, handicrafts, paintings, wall art, etc..are available in online shopping.	.742			
Kitchen items like dinner sets, coffee mugs, cutlery, bar accessories, cooker, kitchen storage.etc. can be purchased through internet.	.821			
Home furnishings like bed sheets, carpets, bedcovers, rugs, towels, etc.. are available in online shopping.	.572			
Electronic items can be purchased in online shopping.	.531			
Kids’ toys are also available in online shopping.	.651			
Jewelleries are available in online websites.	.551			
Accessories like watches, sunglasses, belts, eyeglasses, wallets, pens, key chains, etc. also can be purchased over internet.	.841			
Availability of holiday bookings (Resorts/Rooms)		.682		
Availability of travel tickets.		.721		
Availability of entertainment tickets.		.846		

I am aware of that the payments can be made on delivery of the products.			.651	
Internet banking can be used for online shopping.			.746	
Defective or wrong products can be returned back or exchanged in online shopping.				.842
Online orders can be tracked until it is delivered.				.752
No installation charges for installable items.				.654
Online retailers should have secure payment certificate to assure that the payments are safe.				.952

Source: Using SPSS Statistics 2.0

FACTOR-I:

Fifth factor consist of four variables related to awareness level towards online shopping such as I know groceries items are available in online shopping (.842), Furniture items are available in online shopping (.781) Books and Magazines can also be purchased in internet shopping (.632) Clothing and shoes can be bought through internet (.986) Home decor items like flower and vases, clocks, lights, lamps, handicrafts, paintings, wall art, etc..are available in online shopping (.742) Kitchen items like dinner sets, coffee mugs, cutlery, bar accessories, cooker, kitchen storage.etc. can be purchased through internet (.821) Home furnishings like bed sheets, carpets, bedcovers, rugs, towels, etc.. are available in online shopping (.572) Electronic items can be purchased in online shopping (.531) Kids’ toys are also available in online shopping (.651) Jewelleries are available in online websites (551)and Accessories like watches, sunglasses, belts, eyeglasses, wallets, pens, key chains, etc. also can be purchased over internet (.841)Therefore, all these factors were named as “**Awareness level towards Useable items**”.

FACTOR II:

Second factor consist of two variables namely awareness level towards online shopping such as availability of holiday bookings (.682) availability of travel tickets. (.721 and Availability of entertainment tickets (.846).Therefore, all these factors were named as “**Awareness level towards travel entertainment**”.

FACTOR III:

Third factor consist of two variables namely awareness level towards online shopping such as I am aware of that the payments can be made on delivery of the products (.651) Internet banking can be used for online shopping. (.746).Therefore, all these factors were named as “**Awareness level towards online shopping**”.

FACTOR IV:

Fourth factor consist of four variables related to awareness level towards online shopping such as Defective or wrong products can be returned back or exchanged in online shopping (.842), Online orders can be tracked until it is delivered (.752), No installation charges for installable items(.654) and Online retailers should have secure payment certificate to assure that the payments are safe (.952).Therefore, all these factors were named as “**Awareness level towards online Payment**”.

6.6 OVERALL AWARENESS TOWARDS ONLINE SHOPPING

Table 1.7 explains the overall awareness level of the respondents towards the online shopping

Table 1.7: Overall Awareness towards online shopping

Sl.No	Satisfaction Level	Frequency	Percentage
1	Fully Aware	86	57.3
2	Partly Aware	21	14
3	Somewhat Aware	32	21.3
4	Not Aware	7	4.6
5	Not all Aware	4	2.6
	Total		

Source: primary data

From the table 1.7, it is understood that, 57.3 percent of the respondents are fully aware and the least 2.6 percent of the respondents are not all aware towards the online shopping.

Figure 1.1: Overall Awareness towards online shopping

6.7 DIFERENCE BETWEEN AWARENESS LEVEL TOWARDS ONLINE SHOPPING AND AGE – ONE WAY ANOVA:

In the modern world, peoples are willing to show themselves into updated one and adapt themselves with the modern culture. In order to show themselves into modern one, women’s are buying so many fashion products available in the online. But the reason for purchasing the products by peoples in the online will be differed based the women group they are belongs too. In order to understand the significant difference among the age group of the respondents with respect to the reason for purchasing the fashion products available in the online market, one way A NOVA has been used. The null hypothesis is that there is no significance difference between age and overall awareness level towards online shopping.

Table 1.7: Difference between Awareness Level towards Online Shopping and Age – One Way Anova:

Descriptives								
Age								
Overall Awareness	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Not at all aware	11	1.77	1.113	.120	1.53	2.01	1	4
Somewhat aware	32	2.27	.452	.079	2.11	2.43	2	3
Partly aware	21	3.04	1.232	.233	1.56	2.51	1	4
Fully aware	86	4.00	.000	.000	4.00	4.00	4	4
Total	150	1.97	1.074	.088	1.80	2.15	1	4

Source: Using Spss statistics

Table 1.8: Difference between Awareness Level towards Online Shopping and Age – One Way Anova

ANOVA					
AGE					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	19.035	3	6.345	6.060	.001
Within Groups	152.859	146	1.047		
Total	171.893	149			

Source: Using Spss statistics

Table 1.8 explain the one way ANOVA results that overall awareness level towards online shopping were rejected the null hypothesis, because P value of the variables are less than the benchmark P value of .05. Therefore there is significant difference between age and overall awareness level towards online shopping.

7. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY:

7.1 Findings from Percentage Analysis:

[1] It is found that 67% of customers are male members'. Remaining 33% of customers are female members. Hence it could be said that female members are purchasing through online shopping

[2] It is observed that 47% of sample respondents are belong to the age group below 20 years. 21% are belongs to age group between 21 to 30 years. 20% are belongs to 31 to 40 years and remaining 12% are belongs to 41 to 50 years. Therefore, majority of them were middle age group people.

[3] It is clear that respondents 60% were salaried customers .20% are doing business and 13% belong to the category of farmers .7% are engaged in other occupation. But more number of salaried people are using online shopping.

[4] It is found that majority of customers i.e 60% belonged to Above Rs.25000 income category, 26% of customers earned Rs.10,000 to Rs.15,000 and remaining 10% of customers earned below Rs.10,000 Majority of middle income customers earned above Rs.25000.

7.2 Findings from Friedman test Analysis:

It is observed that from the friedmen test results, the awareness level on various websites available for buying fashion products. Based on the mean rank amazon (10.32) is the top level awareness websites by the customers in the study area, followed by flipkart (8.38), snapdeal (7.27), Jabong (7.14), Myntra (6.34), Yebme (6.17), Cilory (6.06), Ebay (5.89), Shopclues (5.31), Infibeam (5.12), Koovs (5.01) and the last rank is assigned to HomeShop (4.85).

7.3 Findings from Factor Analysis:

From the factor analysis, the variables were grouped into four factors such as awareness level towards Useable items, awareness level towards travel entertainment, awareness level towards online shopping, and awareness level towards online Payment. The most influencing variables is Clothing and shoes can be bought through internet because people were high aware about such variable.

7.4. Findings from Anova:

It is observed that from the one way ANOVA results that overall awareness level towards online shopping were rejected the null hypothesis, because P value of the variables are less than the benchmark P value of .05. Therefore there is significant difference between age and overall awareness level towards online shopping.

8. SUGGESTIONS TO ONLINE MARKETERS:

- ❖ Online marketers can design the awareness programme among the people living in rural areas about online shopping to increase their sales.
- ❖ Membership in online forum is not significantly considered by the respondents while buying the products online.

9. CONCLUSION

The researcher concluded that there is a huge opportunity and gap in Online Shopping Business India. As foreigner players like eBay.com and internet giant Amazon.com is eyeing for Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in online business, competition will be become tougher. Right now Amazon.com has entered but does not sell its own product. They take some commission to sell the product on their platform. The rate of Internet users and Online Shoppers are very high. So the Indian Online Shopping Business is in its Growth state while World's is getting mature. Sivagangai District is one of the Rural district in Tamil Nadu. Even though it is rural district they are prefer to buy products through Online shopping especially, majority of the people purchase their products through online shopping. Therefore, the researcher concluded that in sivagangai District, consumers have more awareness towards online shopping

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